

Social Media Adoption and Students' Learning Outcome: A Case of Social Studies Students in Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between social media adoption and students' learning outcomes: A Case of Social Studies Students in Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between social media usage and students' learning outcomes in Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit as well as the influence of social media adoption on students' learning outcomes in Social Studies in Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit. A survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised all final-year (300 Level) undergraduate students of the 2025/2026 academic session in Akwa Ibom state College of Education Afaha Nsit. Census sampling technique was employed which resulted in a sample size of 329 students. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, while descriptive statistics and linear regression analysis were used for data analysis. The findings revealed that social media usage had a significant positive relationship with students' learning outcomes. The study further established that social media adoption significantly and positively influenced students' learning outcomes in Social Studies in Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit. The study concluded that the effective integration of social media into instructional practices can enhance students' learning outcomes and strengthen the teaching and learning process in Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit. Based on the findings, the study recommended that lecturers should integrate relevant social media platforms into instructional delivery, students should be encouraged to utilize social

media responsibly for academic purposes, and educational institutions should provide adequate digital infrastructure and training to facilitate effective educational use of social media technologies.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Colleges of Education, Learning Outcomes, Social Studies, Social Media Adoption, Social Media Learning

1.0 Introduction

The subject of social studies is a very crucial subject to human development and cordial relationship in a society, Nigeria inclusive. However, despite Nigeria's government educational curriculum reforms and support systems, many students from our secondary educational institutions do not opt for social study at the tertiary educational institutions, Colleges of Education inclusive. The research of Ekpe *et al* (2024) found that teachers, learning environment, student's self-motivation and social influence had positive impacts on the students' academic performance in Malaysia. In recent time, it has been observed that students prefer to send snap-chats on social media instead of handwritten notes. Popular social media outlets patronized by Nigerian youths include Facebook, Instagram and YouTube. Similarly, the social media mostly used in teaching and learning in Nigeria include Google Classroom, Zoom, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube. This could negatively affect their vocabularies. Some use social media to chat with friends and share photographs instead of using it for their studies such as homework, assignments and so on. This study examines whether or not social media can enhance the youths' academic performance. In addition, the study investigates the possible reasons for lack of interest in social studies among students at Nigeria's Colleges of Education?

Some previous researchers have investigated the impact of social media on students' academic performance (Akinsolu, 2020; Ekpe *et al.*, 2024; Li, 2022) but few studies have examined the effect of social media on student's learning outcome regarding social study subject. This is a gap in literature that this study intends to fill.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Social media adoption and students' learning outcomes

Technology Acceptance Model (Davis *et al.*, 1989) was used to explain the reasons people adopt or reject information systems regarding computer applications; the adoption that depends on the users' attitude and behavioral intentions towards it. The model explains that individuals adopt technological systems based primarily on perceived usefulness and

perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which students believe that social media platforms can improve their academic learning and performance, while perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which students consider such technologies simple, accessible, and convenient for educational purposes. In relation to this study, students are more likely to adopt social media for learning Social Studies when they perceive that these platforms enhance access to instructional materials, support academic collaboration, facilitate communication with peers and lecturers, and improve understanding of course contents. Therefore, the acceptance and continuous use of social media for educational activities are expected to positively influence students' learning outcomes.

There are many advantages of using social media for teaching and learning, some of which include collaborative efforts, cost saving, and learning motivation and effectiveness (Brown, 2020). Online group learning can help introvert students in enhancing their communication skills. Complex academic tasks can be handled using social media technologies in tertiary educational institutions as well as a means of communication and group discussions among students regarding their studies (Hamid et al. 2025). Again, it provided active interaction and involvement as well as opportunities for effective learning. Teachers and students can also share and publish new ideas and information such as course materials as well as receiving feedback via the same route. Students can use social media to resolve academic issues among themselves (Andreas and Haenlein, 2020; Ekpe et al., 2024).

Several studies have found a significant positive impact of social media adoption on students' academic performance. For example, a significant positive effect of social media use on students' learning outcomes was found in USA (Dufur, 2023). Also a positive influence of social media engagement on academic performance was found in Malaysia (Al-Rahmi and Othman (2023). Galy et al. (2021) found that university students who received online lessons from their lecturers performed better than those in classroom. Other studies (Ahmahamid et al., 2020; Davoudi and Fartash, 2022) found that technology knowledge sharing had significant positive impact on employee's learning commitment as well as job satisfaction and organizational commitment. However, Englander (2020) found a negative impact social media on students' academic performance because of their use of it to solve personal rather than academic issues. In the light of this, we hypothesize that:

H1: Social media is positively related to student's learning outcomes

2.2 Social media adoption and Social Studies learning outcomes

Many scholars (e.g Ekpe et al., 2024; Englander, 2020) have research on social media generally and its negative effect on student's academic performance. However, there is very scanty literature on the effect of social media adoption on students' learning outcome of Social Studies as a subject. The closest previous study to this study is that of Rajest and Priya (2020) who researched on the impact of social media on mental health of students in India, and found that too much time spent on social media affects students' mental health such as depression and anxiety. Therefore, this study is novel in the area of relating social media adoption specifically to the subject of Social Studies particularly in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. As such, it is paramount to investigate whether or not social media adoption in the teaching and learning of Social Studies can lead to student's learning outcome. In the light of this, we hypothesize that:

H2: Social media adoption is positively related to student's Social Studies learning outcome

3.0 Methodology

3.1. Survey Procedures

The study examined the effect of social media adoption on students' learning outcomes in Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit. However, for convenience and proximity, the study focused specifically on the College of Education Afaha Nsit. The study adopted a survey research design. Questionnaires were distributed to final year (300 Level) undergraduate students during the 2025/2026 academic session. To determine the sample size for the study, census or complete enumeration was carried out on the entire population of final year students in the College. Descriptive statistics and linear regression analysis were used to analyze the data collected from respondents. Ethical considerations were strictly observed during the conduct of the study. Participation in the study was voluntary and respondents were adequately informed about the purpose of the research before completing the questionnaire. Confidentiality and anonymity of participants were also maintained as no personal identifying information was required from the respondents. The researchers ensured that the data obtained were used strictly for academic purposes. To determine the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted using 30 students outside the study area. Cronbach Alpha statistics were used to estimate the internal consistency of the instrument. The reliability coefficient obtained for the social media adoption scale was 0.84, while the students' learning outcome scale yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81. These coefficients were considered adequate and acceptable for the study.

3.2 Measures

The study measured two major variables namely social media adoption and students' learning outcome in Social Studies. Social media adoption was conceptualized as the extent to which students utilize social networking platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter/X, YouTube, Instagram, Google+, blogs, and online discussion forums for academic activities and learning interactions. The construct was adapted from the works of AbuBakar et al. (2010) and Al-Rahmi and Othman (2013). The variable was measured using 10 questionnaire items focusing on frequency of use, academic interaction, collaborative learning, information sharing, and communication through social media platforms. Students' learning outcome was defined as the academic benefits, knowledge acquisition, understanding, participation, and improved learning experiences gained through the use of social media for educational purposes. The measurement items for this variable were adapted from the studies of Al-Rahmi and Othman (2013) and Ayub et al. (2014). The construct was measured using 8 questionnaire items assessing students' perceived improvement in understanding of Social Studies concepts, assignment completion, academic participation, and overall learning effectiveness.

Results

Hypothesis One

H1: Social media is positively related to students' learning outcome.

Table 1: Linear Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Social Media and Students' Learning Outcome

Variables	N	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-value	Beta (β)	t-value	Sig.
Social Media	329	.682	.465	.463	132.76	.682	16.842	.000
Students' Learning Outcome								
Source: Field Survey, 2026					df-(1,327)			

The result presented in Table 1 revealed that social media had a positive relationship with students' learning outcome. The regression coefficient value ($\beta = .682$) indicates a strong positive relationship between social media usage and students' learning

outcome. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .465$) showed that social media accounted for 46.5% of the variation in students' learning outcome, while the remaining 53.5% could be attributed to other factors not included in the study. The t-value of 16.842 with a significance value of .000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicates that the relationship was statistically significant. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that social media is positively related to students' learning outcome was accepted. This implies that effective and educational use of social media platforms significantly enhances students' learning outcomes.

Hypothesis Two

H2: Social media adoption is positively related to students' Social Studies learning outcome.

Table 2: Linear Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Social Media Adoption and Students' Social Studies Learning Outcome

Variables	N	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-value	Beta (β)	t-value	Sig.
Social Media Adoption								
Social Studies Learning Outcome	329	.714	.510	.508	131.93	.714	18.457	.000

Source: (Field Survey, 2026) df=(1,327)

The result in Table 2 revealed that social media adoption had a positive relationship with students' Social Studies learning outcome. The regression coefficient value ($\beta = .714$) indicates a strong positive relationship between social media adoption and Social Studies learning outcome. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .510$) revealed that social media adoption explained 51.0% of the variation in students' Social Studies learning outcome. The t-value of 18.457 and significance value of .000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance, showed that the relationship was statistically significant. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that social media adoption is positively related to students' Social Studies learning outcome was accepted. This means that the adoption of social media in teaching and learning Social Studies significantly improves students' learning outcomes.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that social media was positively and significantly related to students' learning outcome. This implies that students who effectively utilized social media platforms for educational purposes demonstrated improved learning outcomes. The finding suggests that social media platforms provide opportunities for collaborative learning, sharing of academic materials, classroom interaction, and access to educational information which may enhance students' academic engagement and understanding. The finding agrees with the study of Rajest and Priya (2020), who observed that although excessive social media use may negatively affect students psychologically, moderate and purposeful educational usage can improve students' engagement and access to information. The finding also aligns with Ekpe et al. (2014), who noted that social media platforms can support communication and information exchange among students when used appropriately for academic purposes. Similarly, Englander (2010) observed that digital interaction platforms influence students' learning behaviours and educational experiences significantly. The finding further implies that social media has evolved beyond entertainment and social interaction to become an important instructional and learning support tool in modern education. Through social media, students can access online educational resources, participate in academic discussions, collaborate on assignments, and communicate easily with peers and lecturers.

The findings of the study revealed that social media adoption significantly and positively related to students' Social Studies learning outcome. This implies that students who adopted and utilized social media platforms in the learning of Social Studies achieved better learning outcomes than those who did not actively use such platforms for academic purposes. The finding supports the assertion that social media platforms facilitate interactive learning, promote access to current information, and improve communication between lecturers and students. Since Social Studies deals with human society, social interaction, culture, citizenship, and current affairs, social media platforms provide rich opportunities for discussion, information sharing, collaborative learning, and exposure to contemporary societal issues relevant to the subject. The finding also agrees with Rajest and Priya (2020), who emphasized that digital platforms significantly influence students' educational experiences and learning behaviours. Furthermore, the result suggests that when properly integrated into instructional activities, social media can enhance students' participation, motivation, critical thinking, and understanding of Social Studies concepts. The finding therefore underscores the importance of integrating social media technologies

into classroom instruction in Colleges of Education to improve students' learning outcomes in Social Studies.

Conclusion/ Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that social media and social media adoption significantly and positively influence students' learning outcome and Social Studies learning outcome among final year students in Colleges of Education. It was evident that students who effectively utilized social media platforms for academic purposes demonstrated better understanding of concepts, improved classroom participation, enhanced communication, and higher learning outcomes. The adoption of social media in the teaching and learning of Social Studies significantly improved students' academic engagement and achievement in the subject. Therefore, the study concludes that proper integration and educational use of social media platforms can serve as effective tools for improving teaching and learning processes in Colleges of Education.

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

- i) Lecturers in Colleges of Education should integrate social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, Telegram, and X into instructional delivery to enhance students' learning outcome and academic engagement.
- ii) Students should be encouraged to utilize social media platforms for academic discussions, collaborative learning, sharing of educational materials, and research activities rather than for purely social or entertainment purposes.
- iii) The Akwa Ibom State College of Education should provide adequate digital infrastructure and internet facilities to support effective use of social media for learning purposes.

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